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FINANCIAL INCLUSION AND REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

National economic growth is accompanied by an intensified polarization among region and an increase in disparities among them. Only in a few countries national economic growth is accompanied by a narrowing of regional imbalances. The benefits of economic growth and financial sector reforms will trickle down to common people only after having balanced regional development. The paper finds out the reason of regional disparities and attempts to have balanced regional development through financial inclusion. It is found that one of the way through which balanced regional development could be achieved is better access to credit and financial services. The paper reveals that with an increase in income, loan taken from bank instead of money lender increases. This multiplier effect disperses benefits of economic growth to all sections of society and to different regions of the nation through financial inclusion. The paper concludes by suggesting that it may be time to consider financial inclusion in terms of generating income if balanced regional development is to be a priority.

Keywords: inclusion, regional development, bank, disparities, monetary.

Introduction

For several decades, the Indian economy was almost stagnant, developing at a rate barely exceeding the growth of population. Over the past decade it has advanced at an average rate of about 4 per cent per annum, the increase in aggregate national income being about 42 per cent. This modest increase in national income does not give a full indication of the growth potential of the economy built up especially during the Second Plan. While the income from agriculture and allied sectors, which accounts for almost one-half of the national income, has increased by a little over a third plan, the total income from the organised manufacturing sector has nearly doubled. Even within the sector of organised industry, the growth of the investment goods industries has been considerably faster than the average. However, as the increase in population has been greater than had been anticipated, income per head has increased only by about 16 per cent. Over the same period, due to the rapid progress of science and technology and the rates of growth secured in the advanced countries, the disparities between them and the less developed countries have widened. A widespread perception all over the country is that disparities among States, and regions within States, between urban and rural areas, and between various sections of the community, have been steadily increasing in the past few years and that the gains of the rapid growth witnessed in XI plan period have not reached all parts of the country and all sections of the people in an equitable manner. That this perception is well founded is borne by available statistics on a number of indicators. Though there is some evidence to indicate

a movement towards convergence on human development indicators across States, one of the reasons for this convergence could also be that most human development indicators have a value cap. However, widening income differentials between more developed and relatively poorer States is a matter of serious concern. The economic growth or decline in many countries is spread unequally over the regions of the country. In most countries, national economic growth is accompanied by an intensified polarization among regions and an increase in the disparities among them. Realising these facts whole section in the XI Plan document of Government of India has been attributed to “Towards faster and More Inclusive Growth.” Inclusive growth in the XI Plan is defined as ‘growth process which yields broad based benefits and ensures equality of opportunity for all,’ it stands for ‘equitable growth or development with social justice’ which have always been the watch words for development planning in India (Eleventh Five Year Plan).

Financial inclusion is not only about credit and number of bank accounts held by the weaker sections. Financial inclusion has been defined as ‘the process of ensuring access to appropriate financial products and services needed by all sections of the society in general and vulnerable groups such as weaker sections and low income groups in particular, at an affordable cost, in a fair and transparent manner, by regulated, mainstream institutional players’. Financial Inclusion is important not only from the perspective of the benefit it provides to the poor but also from the perspective of overall stability of the social and economic system of the country. Financial Inclusion of the poor has a multiplier effect on the economy as a whole, through higher savings pooled from the vast segments of the population present at the bottom of the pyramid. There is a potential for transforming the lives of these excluded groups by providing access to formal savings arrangements and extension of credit by banks for emergency and entrepreneurial purposes, thereby enabling the poor to create assets, generate stable income, build resilience to meet macro-economic and livelihood shocks and bring about an improvement in their financial condition and living standards (Chakrabarty, 2013: 117).

There is now a genuine and widespread recognition about the adverse social consequences of rising inequalities in the recent high growth phase, which do not seem to be mitigated through the so called ‘trickle-down’ mechanism (Pal, 2011:80). Only in a few countries national economic growth is accompanied by a narrowing of regional disparities. Balanced development of different parts of the country, extension of the benefits of economic progress to the less developed regions and widespread diffusion of industry are among the major aims of planned development. Successive Five Year Plans seek to realise these aims in larger measure. Expansion of the economy and more rapid growth increase progressively the capacity to achieve a better balance between national and regional development. In striving for such a balance, certain inherent difficulties have to be met, especially in the early phases of economic development. As resources are limited, frequently advantage lies in concentrating them at those points within the economy at which the returns are likely to be favourable. As development proceeds investments are undertaken over a wider area and resources can be applied at a large number of points, thereby resulting in greater spread of benefits. In the interest of development itself, the maximum increase in national income should be achieved and resources obtained for further investment. The process is a cumulative one, each stage determining the shape of the next. In some fields, as in industry, intensive and localised development may be inevitable. Along with this, in other areas, the aim should be to provide for more dispersed advance in sectors like agriculture, small industries, power, communications and social services. Equally with industry, investment in economic and social overheads helps to create numerous promising centres for growth. Once a minimum in terms of national income and growth in different sectors is reached, without affecting the progress of the economy as a whole, it becomes possible to provide in many directions for a larger scale of development in the less developed regions.

A large country with extensive natural resources, viewing each phase of its development in the perspective of a long-term plan, has the means not only to realise a high and sustained rate of growth but also to enable its less developed regions to come up to the level of the

rest. How does one define and measure the "level of development"? Is the level of development of a region the same as its level of well-being, and if so, how does one measure "regional well-being"? Should the "level of development" of a region be determined by objective or subjective variables, or based on indicators that take both into account? Does regional inequality with respect to the level of development increase or decrease over time? Is there a difference in this respect between developed and developing countries? What are the factors that produce spatial polarity with respect to the "level of development", and what research methodologies should be used to identify these factors? Should one only use the data that are published in most countries based on administrative geographical units, or are these units irrelevant to this sort of research, in which case one must construct a database using economic geographical units? The author has tried to answer these questions by taking literacy and banking accessibility as variables to define the level of development.

Objectives

1. To study the factors responsible for regional imbalances in the economy;
2. To find out solutions for regional imbalances;
3. To examine relationship between socio-economic indicators and monetary trends with reference to balanced regional development.

Literature Survey

Data on population, literacy ratio, bank offices, and bank credit of public sector bank is available from Economic survey 2012-13, Government of India and data for net state domestic production at factor cost, and percentage of person below poverty line of different states of India is retrieved from Handbook of Statistics on the Indian economy 2012. The Handbook of Statistics on the Indian Economy is a flagship publication of the Reserve Bank, which provides long historical time series data on a wide range of financial and economic indicators pertaining to national income aggregates, output, prices, money, banking, financial markets, public finances, foreign trade, balance of payments and select socio-economic indicators, which are released at various frequencies. The data for bank credit represents the gross bank credit of public sector bank at end March 2012. The data regarding net state domestic production at factor cost (NSDP_{FC}) is calculated at constant price based on base year 2004-05 for 2011-12. The figure of this data is retrieved from Handbook of Statistics on the Indian economy 2012 where figure is given in rupees billion. The author has converted this to rupees crore. Currently, a minimum consumption expenditure, anchored in an average (food) energy adequacy norm of 2400 and 2100 calories per capita per day is used to define State specific poverty lines, separately for rural and urban areas. These poverty lines are then applied on the NSSO's household consumer expenditure distributions to estimate the proportion and number of poor at the State level (Handbook of Statistics of Indian Economy, 2012:406). Percentage of persons below poverty line in different states is retrieved from Handbook of Statistics on the Indian economy 2012. The percentage of persons below poverty line is for year 2004-05 based on uniform recall period consumption expenditure. Data on income and bank accounts, and income and access to loan is retrieved from various issues of Reserve Bank of India bulletin. The Reserve Bank of India Bulletin is a monthly bulletin published by the Department of Economic and Policy Research, Reserve Bank of India.

Chakrabarty (February 2013:115) finds that though rural inhabitants have largely remained the focus of our financial inclusion efforts since a large proportion of our villages are still unbanked, the ground reality, however, is that the problem of exclusion is widespread even in urban areas, especially, for the disadvantaged and low-income groups, despite there being no dearth of bank branches. Chakrabarty (January 2013:12) talked about complete transformation of banking system during the last two decades. Banks have sought to grow, not just in terms of balance sheet size, but also in terms of greater penetration of banking services to the hitherto unbanked segments of the population. Meeting the expectations of this group through financial inclusion efforts presents a huge business opportunity for banks in his paper entitled "Contemporary Issues in Banking: Reflections on Viewpoints of Bank Economists" published in RBI monthly bulletin, January 2013. Gokarn (April

2011:485) analysis various attributes of consumer behaviour and motivations, which he believe are important inputs into devising a strategy for commercially viable financial inclusion. Pal (2011:80) talks about transformation of banking system from beyond brick and mortar branches to adopt innovative delivery channels including internet banking, ATMs, call centres, kiosks, Business Correspondents (BCs), etc. These new products are working as strong inputs for rural development through financial inclusion.

The above review brings out different aspects of financial inclusion through which different sectors of the economy could get benefit from economic growth. I have not found any study which link financial inclusion with balanced regional development. Out of the review of the studies presented above, Gokarn (2011:485) has focused on penetration of various financial products and services among different class of people. He studies financial inclusion from employment perspective. He believes that better access to financial services would help to increase the livelihood potential of a number of occupational categories, which in turn would help reduce the income differentials between casual labour workforce and salaried and more regular jobs. One of the different aspects of inclusiveness is inclusiveness and regional balance, which is being discussed in detail in Twelfth Five Year Plan 2012-17, Planning commission, government of India.

The present study therefore makes a contribution in respect of four specific aspects viz., (i) financial inclusion does not require physical banking facility in every habitation, (ii) pointing out the areas in which scope for improvement in data collection/publication practices exist., (iii) suggesting directions for policy formulation which could contribute to increasing the share of low income group and disadvantage group in the economy, and (iv) giving food for thought that increase in net state domestic production through financial inclusion could bring balanced regional development.

Data Base and Data Analysis

For the purpose of this study, data on income and bank accounts, and income and access to loan is retrieved from various issues of Reserve Bank of India bulletin like RBI Monthly Bulletin of April 2011, January 2013, and February 2013. Data on socio-economic indicators and monetary trends like: population, literacy ratio, percentage of person below poverty line and net state domestic production at factor cost, number of bank offices, and bank credit of different states/union territories of India has been retrieved from Economic Survey 2012-13, Government of India and Handbook of Statistics on the Indian economy 2012, Reserve Bank of India .Some data in the text are retrieved from different Five Year Plan, Planning commission, Government of India. The author has attempted to find out if there is any relationship exists between balanced regional development and socio economic indicators like population, literacy rate, and percentage of person living below poverty line; and monetary trends like number of bank offices, net state domestic production at factor cost, and bank credit.

In this analysis, the author has assumed all states and union territories of India as region (Region in oxford dictionary is defined as an area of a country or the world having definable characteristics but not always fixed boundaries). It is also assumed that high banking penetration, and highest credit availability leads to low poverty, which ultimately indicates low regional imbalances. This study is comparative analysis of data of specific states. The comparative study of Uttar Pradesh and Maharashtra states that regional inequality and poverty is low where credit availability is high in proportion to population for example credit availability to Maharashtra as compared to Uttar Pradesh is high. As a result Net state domestic product at factor cost is high in Maharashtra and poverty is low as compared to Uttar Pradesh.

The analysis of data of two states is comparative and it is true for these states only. In general this would not work, as Maharashtra is highest in both availability of bank credit and Net state domestic production at factor cost yet poverty is not low. It is Punjab where poverty is low. Latest data of Maharashtra is not available. Therefore, author has used data

for the year 2010-11 for both states Maharashtra and Uttar Pradesh. Except these two states, Table 4 is providing latest data for all states and union territories i.e., for year 2011-12. Percentage of person below poverty line is based uniform recall period for the year 2004-05. This percentage is a combination of both rural and urban area. When consumer expenditure data for all the items are collected from 30-day recall period, we call it uniform recall period consumption. In mixed recall period consumption, consumer expenditure data for five non-food items, namely, clothing, footwear, durable goods, education and institutional medical expenses are collected from 365-day recall period and the consumption data for the remaining items are collected from 30-day recall period.

Causes of Regional Inequalities

If labour and capital grow at the same rate, the nation's production frontier will shift out evenly in all directions at the rate of factor growth. As a result the slope of the old and new production frontiers (before and after factor) growth will be the same at any point where they are cut by a ray from the origin. This is the case of balanced growth (Salvatore, 2004: 201). This balanced growth is not happening in India. Regional imbalances or disparities as existing in a country like India are mostly influenced by variety of factors, ranging from historical, geographical, and economic to even political factors. Historically, regional imbalances in India started from the British regime. British industrialists mostly preferred to concentrate their activities in two states like West Bengal and Maharashtra and more particularly to three metropolitan cities like Calcutta, Mumbai, and Chennai. Besides, other factors like geographical factors, locational advantages, inadequacy of economic overheads, lack of growth of ancillary industries in backward states, inclination of backward states towards political intrigues and manipulations instead of industrial development, restrained access to bank credit, and political instability are responsible for regional imbalances in India. India is facing the problem of acute regional imbalances and the indicators of such imbalances are reflected by the factors like per capita income, the proportion of population living below the poverty line, the percentage of urban population of total population, percentage of population working in primary sector, secondary sector, and tertiary sector, pace of industrialisation, educational status, employment opportunities and earning potential.

The ultimate goal of development policy, of which financial inclusion is a critical component, is to raise the incomes of as many households as possible in a sustainable way. There is of course, no iron law, which says that incomes earned by all occupations must be equal. Differentials that emerge from qualifications, skills, productivity and value-added are all legitimate in a market economy, in which financial incentives drive resource allocations across alternative activities. However, from policy perspective, we must also be conscious of barriers and bottlenecks, which impede the productivity and, consequently, the earning potential from different activities. In India, there are a number of regions or States within a region, or even districts within a State, where development outcomes, in terms of social indicators, do not match with the available resources and the inherent potential of the people. States that are rich in minerals are not necessarily industrially developed, and those with rich cultivable lands and assured irrigation are often lagging behind in agricultural development. There are States in the country that have been able to achieve significant gains in overall development, while others have squandered opportunities despite their natural advantage and favourable initial conditions. Disparities in regional development exist because of the following reason:

- Poor management of economies, persisting fiscal imbalances, disparities in the pace and level of development across regions and across districts;
- Denial of basic needs of food, water and shelter to a substantial proportion of the population;
- Threat to life and personal security in the face of inadequate State control on law and order; marginalisation, exclusion or even persecution of people on account of social, religious, castes or even gender affiliations;

- Lack of sensitivity, transparency and accountability in many facets of the working of State machinery, particularly those that have an interface with the public;
- Lack of credibility – the gap between the intent and the actions- of some institutions in society;
- Inadequate system of incentives/disincentives for people (particularly for a civil servant), subversion of rules, evasion of taxes and failure in getting timely justice;
- Existence of a significant number of voiceless poor with little opportunities for participating even in institutions of local self-governance, despite a visible movement towards decentralisation through the Panchayati Raj institutions; and
- Deterioration of physical environment, particularly in urban areas (X Five Year Plan),and
- Restrained access to public goods and services and lack of accessibility to credit availability and financial services.

The Current Status of Inclusion

The benefits of economic growth and financial sector reforms will trickle down to common people only after having balanced regional development. Balanced regional development requires long-run economic management policy. But the short run has to be a bridge to the long run. Productive jobs are vital for development and are the best form of inclusion, but the central long-run question facing India is where will good jobs come from? More than half our population depends on agriculture, but the experience of other countries suggests that the number of people depends on agriculture will have to shrink if per capita incomes in agriculture are to go up substantially. While industry is creating jobs, too many such jobs are low productivity non-contractual jobs in the unorganized sector, offering low incomes, little protection, and no benefits. Service jobs are relatively high productivity, but employment growth in services has been slow in recent years. India's challenge is to create the conditions for faster growth of productive jobs outside of agriculture, especially in organized manufacturing and in services, even while improving productivity in agriculture (Economic Survey, 2012-13:26).

Efficient intermediation by financial markets leads to higher economic growth by increasing savings and their optimal allocation for productive uses. With the start of the reform process beginning 1990s, the importance and nature of financial intermediation has undergone a transformation with other intermediaries including non-banking financial companies (NBFCs), insurance and pension funds, and mutual funds(MF) emerging as the new mechanisms for channelling savings to investments. These developments have also been accompanied by the emergence of equity and debt markets, financial products like forwards, futures and other derivatives instruments, which have the capacity of reallocating risks and putting capital to more efficient use. However, keeping in view India's growing integration with global financial markets, external-sectors vulnerabilities have an increasingly large impact on India through the trade and capital account channels. It is therefore important that the development of an efficient and healthy financial market should also be accompanied by an effective regulatory mechanism that keeps track of external vulnerabilities (Economic Survey 2012-13, 105).

The benefits of financial sector reforms have been visible in the step up in India's growth trajectory. Along with higher growth, better distribution of the benefits of growth across different sections of the society and regions so as to contain inequality, reduce the incidence of poverty and improve the employment situation also needs to be pursued. One of the avenues through which balanced regional development could be achieved is better access to credit and financial services. The potential of the financial system has not been harnessed fully due to the extent of the financial exclusion prevailing today (Pal, 2013:119-126).

Education is of basic importance in the regional development of a nation. In a democratic set up, the role of education becomes crucial, since it can function effectively only if there is an intelligent participation of the masses in the affairs of the country. The

success of planning in a democracy depends also on the growth of the spirit of co-operation and the sense of disciplined citizenship among the people and on the degree to which it becomes possible to evoke public enthusiasm and build up local leadership. The educational system should also satisfy cultural needs, which is essential for the healthy growth of a nation. The system should stimulate the growth of the creative faculties, increase the capacity for enjoyment and develop a spirit of critical appreciation of arts, literature and other creative activities. The fulfilment of the objectives mentioned above, will lead to the development of an integrated personality in the individual, which should be the first and foremost aim of any system of education. Education and skill development are the basic challenges for regional development. Education here means quality education. The demographic change will generate a huge scope for quality education but the demographic dividend can be reaped only if we can make quality education affordable. Technology and innovation in banking can make such education accessible and affordable by bringing down the unit cost of quality education (Chakrabarty, 2011: : 1057).

Table 1: Indicators of Developments in Different States

Name of State	Population In Thousand Year 2001	Literacy Rate (Per cent) Year 2001	NSDP _{FC} ^f (Rs. Crore) Year 2011-12	Number of Bank Offices at the end of March 2012	Bank ^h Credit at end March 2012 (Rs. crore)	Percentage Persons Below Poverty Line ^g 2004-05
Andhra Pradesh	76210	60.47	363835	5869	305304	15.80
Arunachal Pradesh	1098 ^a	54.34	5327	71	1327	17.60
Assam	26656 ^b	63.25	70683	1110	20230	19.70
Bihar	82999	47.00	150398	2997	32964	41.40
Chhattisgarh	20834	64.66	75570	1009	31468	40.90
Goa	1348	82.01	20216	410	8414	13.80
Gujarat	50671	69.14	-	4298	170750	16.80
Haryana	21145	67.91	161937	2162	128213	14.00
Himachal Pradesh	6078	76.48	34379	957	13132	10.00
Jammu & Kashmir	10144 ^c	55.52	34157	383	3746	5.40
Jharkhand	26946	53.56	72660	1660	25990	40.30
Karnataka	52851	66.64	248354	4744	213433	25.00
Kerala	31841	90.86	185434	2868	98690	15.00
Madhya Pradesh	60348	63.74	-	3363	79878	38.30
Maharashtra	96879	76.88	702832 ⁱ	7170	947948	30.70
Manipur	2294 ^d	70.53 ^e	6868	61	1228	17.30
Meghalaya	2319	62.56	10277	164	2458	18.50
Mizoram	889	88.80	-	43	901	12.60
Nagaland	1990	66.59	8284	85	1508	19.00
Odisha	36805	63.08	113587	2195	48564	46.40
Punjab	24359	69.65	138061	3510	126875	8.40
Rajasthan	56507	60.41	-	3166	111772	22.10
Sikkim	541	68.81	-	80	1199	20.10
Tamil Nadu	62406	73.45	382229	5359	322799	22.50
Tripura	3199	73.19	14714	141	1957	18.90
Uttar Pradesh	166198	56.27	345848 ^j	8180	157545	32.80
Uttarakhand	8489	71.62	47983	1101	17231	39.60
West Bengal	80176	68.64	308018	4635	196191	24.70
Andaman & Nicobar Islands	356	81.30	2697	44	768	22.60
Chandigarh	901	81.94	-	301	39745	7.10
Dadra & Nagar Haveli	220	57.63	-	25	364	33.20
Daman and Diu	158	78.18	-	25	344	10.50
Delhi	13851	81.67	201653	2145	473643	14.70
Lakshadweep	61	86.66	-	12	55	16.00
Puducherry	974	81.24	10279	112	3874	22.40
All India	1028737 ^d	64.84	-	70455	3590508	27.50

Source: Compiled from Economic Survey 2012-13, Government of India and Handbook of Statistics of Indian Economy 2011-12, Reserve Bank of India.

Note:

a. Census conducted for the first time in 1961.

- b. The 1981 Census could not be held in Assam. Total population for 1981 has been worked out by interpolation.
- c. The 1991 Census could not be held in Jammu & Kashmir. Total population for 1991 has been worked out by Interpolation.
- d. India and Manipur figures include estimated population for those of the three sub-divisions viz. Mao Maram, Paomata and Purul Senapati district of Manipur as census results of 2001 in these three sub-divisions were cancelled due to technical and administrative reasons.
- e. All India and Manipur figures exclude those of the three sub-divisions of Manipur viz. Mao Maram, Paomata and Purul of Senapati district of Manipur as census results of 2001 in these three sub-divisions were cancelled due to technical and administrative reasons.
- f. Net State Domestic Product at Factor Cost (At constant Prices), base year 2004-05.
- g. Rural and urban combined, based on URP consumption.
- h. Gross bank credit of public sector banks.
- i. Data is for year 2010-11. Data for year 2011-12 is not available.
- j. Data is for year 2010-11. Data for year 2011-12 is Rs.367185 crore.

Education, skill development and banking penetration can help reducing regional imbalance development in the economy. Not only education but quality education along with technology development and participation of masses in growth could bring regional balance development. This is possible through financial inclusion which is shown in Table 1. Table 1 indicates different parameters of balanced regional development. If we compare Uttar Pradesh and Odisha we find that in Odisha literacy ratio is 63.08 per cent and number of percentage of persons living below poverty line is 46.40 while in Uttar Pradesh literacy ratio is 56.27 per cent which is lower as compared to Odisha and number of percentage of persons living below poverty line in is 32.80 per cent which is lower as compared to Odisha. This is because in Uttar Pradesh though literacy ratio is lower as compared to Odisha but banking penetration is higher in Uttar Pradesh. In Uttar Pradesh number of bank branches is 8180 while in Odisha it is only 2195. As a result net state domestic product at factor cost in Uttar Pradesh is Rs. 367185 crores while in Odisha net state domestic product at factor cost is low as compared to Rs. 113587 crores. Bank credit available to Uttar Pradesh is Rs. 157545 crores, which is high as compared to Odisha where availability of bank credit is only Rs. 48564 crores. This table indicates that regional inequality and poverty is low where credit availability is high in proportion to population for example credit availability to Maharashtra is Rs. 947948 crores is high as compared to Uttar Pradesh. As a result Net state domestic product at factor cost is high in Maharashtra and poverty is low as compared to Uttar Pradesh. This table also indicates that opening of bank branches is not as important as availability of bank credit for instance in Uttar Pradesh number of bank branches is high but availability of bank credit to Uttar Pradesh is low as compared to Maharashtra, where number of bank branches is low as compared to Uttar Pradesh.

The overall disparity in inter-state growth of NSDP and per capita NSDP of States has increased considerably during the nineties as compared to the seventies and eighties. Decade of the eighties seems to be a period in which horizontal inequity across States was a minimum compared to other periods. In the nineties the magnitude of disparities was the maximum. It may be seen that less developed regions including the north eastern States, Orissa and the heartland States of Bihar, Uttar Pradesh and Madhya Pradesh have generally recorded growth rates below the All-India average during the most recent period of 1993-94 to 1998-1999. This trend suggests a widening of the gap between the more and the less developed States. The growth experience of the nineties has two alternative interpretations. One, that the faster growth experienced in some States is at the expense of others and is an outcome of a lessening of the equalising role of centralised planning. Alternatively, it could be argued that the reformed economic climate allowed some individual States to harness more of their true economic potential; this was not at the expense of other States. The national average growth stepped up by 1 percentage point in the nineties, and most States experienced improved growth in this decade (Tenth Five Year Plan).

The factor, which determines the long term conditions of growth are the demographic trends, the basic resource endowments, the entrepreneurial resources and the technology perspective. The growth, size and structure of population and growth of labour force are the elements of demographic trends, which determine the long-term social needs on the one hand and influence the growth prospects on the other. Basic resource endowments i.e., the sources of energy, land, water, other essential minerals, environment and ecology are vital elements in the determination of the potential for growth and comparative advantage. However, technology can augment the basic resources by raising their productivity, and conserving their uses. Access to the best technology in all spheres of activity and ability to take a lead in building up new technologies (i.e., making innovations) even in a small sphere of activity are going to become the most crucial factors in determining our development pace viz-a-viz other countries.(Eighth Five Year Plan).All these requires accessibility to education and bank credit. Availability of bank credit and education to this population will ensure balanced regional growth.

Strategy for Balanced Regional Growth

Economy growth though important cannot be an end in itself. Higher standards of living as well as of development opportunities for all, stemming from the greater resources generated by economic growth, are the ultimate aim of development policy. This implies the need to bridge regional, social and economic disparities, as well as the empowerment of the poor and marginalized, especially women to make the entire development process more inclusive (Economic Survey 2012-13: 269). Financial literacy has emerged as a focus area for policy makers not just in India, but all across the globe, particularly in the aftermath of the global financial crisis. World bank group and International Monetary fund is ready to take up the challenge of supporting countries in reaching their financial inclusion targets and accelerating progress toward reducing the 2.5 billion people without access to financial services today (www.gpfi.org). Success in dissemination of financial literacy has been identified as key to meeting the critical objectives of financial inclusion and consequently, financial stability (Chakrabarty, 2013:1). One should keep in mind three prerequisites for having balanced regional development through financial inclusion. These are: i. holistic approach to provision of financial services, not just credit or deposit alone; ii. meeting the needs of small firms, and iii. focussing on segments of population excluded by gender or geographical remoteness (Chakrabarty, 2013: 15).

Financial landscape in urban areas is completely different from that in rural areas. If, indeed, lack of access to financial services is a significant reason for the persistence of earnings differentials in urban areas, then it suggests that a relatively well penetrated environment is also not delivering inclusion to its potential. If this is the case, then we must be cautious in linking the mere presence of financial service providers with the achievement of financial inclusion. The strategy must go beyond organisational presence to the design of appropriate products and services. Every aspect of financial inclusion strategy whether it is the design of products, and services, or the delivery mechanism needs to be viewed in terms of the business opportunities and investment dimensions. Financial service providers must see inclusion as a business opportunity that it offers and not as an obligation that has been imposed on the service providers. Financial sector has to design and deliver appropriate products and services to a very large number of potential customers to bridge the gap between developed and under developed region.

From the point view of expenditure, the household spend largest segment of his income on food. This expenditure on food goes down as income goes up what is called as Engel's law in economics but at the aggregate level, the proportion is significant. We are considering here unusual expenditures by households, which essentially means that these expenditures are generally incurred, but not on a regular or predictable basis. The pattern suggests that the most significant unusual expenditure by far is on ceremonies and on medical expenses. The two categories together accounted for almost 80 per cent of unusual expenditures across all households (Gokarn, 2011:489). Given the significance of these two expenditures, particularly amongst lower income households the medical expense could be

borne by health insurance product. The need to develop a financial buffer for expenditures related to ceremonies, though more complicated than health insurance. These types of expenditures may be covered by systematic investment plan. Product of this nature are already available in the market: the question is, essentially, one of threshold contributions and whether they can be lowered to provide access to large numbers of households, even while giving them a reasonable rate of return so there is sufficient accumulation. The Indian Financial System currently offers a variety of products and services, but threshold requirements apply, which means that many lower income households, whose motivations are the same as those of more affluent ones, cannot access the same products and services. One could argue that there are no products and services which can meet these requirements with commercial viability. But this is a proposition that needs to be explored (Gokarn, 2011:491). Why people borrowed money? Considering all loans taken by the households surveyed, over 50 per cent of rural households and about 45 per cent of urban households report that they borrowed money to deal with financial and medical emergencies. Business purposes were also significant, but not dominant. Of course, since lending money to enable people to deal with such situations is not the conventional activity of banking or most other formal financial service providers, it is unlikely that this requirement would be met by this category of lenders. This questions whether right kinds of product exist to expand the coverage to households that are currently excluded from access to credit.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Development of regions and of the national economy as a whole has to be viewed as parts of a single process. The progress of the national economy should be reflected in the rate of growth realised by different regions and, in turn, greater development of resources in the regions must contribute towards accelerating the rate of progress for the country as a whole. Excessive emphasis on the problems of particular regions and attempts to plan for their development without relating their needs to the requirements of the national economy have to be guarded against, for, in the final analysis, it is as integral parts of the country that different regions can best hope to realise their full potential for growth. Balanced regional growth emerges eventually from a whole series of connected developments, many of which are of a long-term character. Connected development is based on financial inclusion through bank credit availability by a mechanism called 'priority sector lending' through which credit is channelled to certain preferred sectors, which inter alia, include small scale industry, small business and agriculture. Bank credit must be available to the different region and the poor at reasonable rate of interest so that they can avail the credit. This is true for individual, regions and, equally, for the national economy as a whole. Whatever the present shortcomings, the aim must be that over a reasonable period all regions in the country should realise their potential for economic development and should attain levels of living not far removed from those of the nation as a whole. Progress in different regions must therefore, be watched carefully and additional steps must be taken to speed up development in particular areas, which are found to be seriously lagging behind. The paper finds that there is a direct relationship between income level and access to loan. This does not mean that lowest income group household does not need credit. If the bank doesn't meet their requirements, they are clearly accessing other sources. They may be relatives, friends, and money lenders etc. It is found that there is an inverse relationship between income and loan taken from money lenders. It is found that regional inequality and poverty is low where credit availability is high in proportion to population for example credit availability to Maharashtra is high as compared to Uttar Pradesh. As a result net state domestic production at factor cost is high in Maharashtra and poverty is low as compared to Uttar Pradesh. Opening of bank branches is not as important as availability of bank credit for instance in Uttar Pradesh number of bank branches is high but availability of bank credit to Uttar Pradesh is low as compared to Maharashtra. The paper concludes that access to quality education, banking facilities and availability of credit along with increasing income level will not only help poor people to get rid from the clutches of money lenders but also help to contain regional inequality. The opening up of no-frills account has certainly propelled number of saving accounts in banks, but India needs to give focused attention on

how to use financial inclusion as strategy to increase income of the people. What is required today is to bring the level of governance on a par with the level of the economy to contain regional inequality.

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